

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN OPHTHALMOLOGY

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Abstract. In recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) has become increasingly important in ophthalmology, opening up new opportunities for the early diagnosis, monitoring, and prognosis of ophthalmic diseases. This article examines modern methods for applying AI, including machine learning and deep neural networks, to the analysis of ophthalmic images, such as fundus photographs, optical coherence tomography, and ultrasound data. Particular attention is paid to the use of AI for the detection of glaucoma, diabetic retinopathy, age-related macular degeneration, and other common eye diseases. The advantages and limitations of implementing intelligent systems in clinical practice, as well as issues of accuracy, interpretability, and the integration of AI solutions into existing diagnostic processes, are also analyzed. The results of the study confirm the high potential of artificial intelligence as an effective tool for supporting medical decision-making and improving the quality of ophthalmic care.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, ophthalmology, machine learning, deep neural networks, medical images, eye disease diagnostics, glaucoma, diabetic retinopathy, optical coherence tomography, clinical decision support.

Introduction

Ophthalmology is one of the most dynamically developing fields of medicine, as eye diseases significantly impact quality of life and, in some cases, lead to irreversible vision loss. According to the World Health Organization, millions of people worldwide suffer from conditions such as glaucoma, diabetic retinopathy, and age-related macular degeneration, and the effectiveness of treatment depends largely on timely and accurate diagnosis.

In recent years, the rapid development of digital technologies and medical data processing methods has facilitated the active implementation of artificial intelligence in clinical practice. Artificial intelligence, including machine learning and deep neural networks, has demonstrated high efficiency in analyzing large volumes of medical data, particularly in pattern recognition and image classification. This makes ophthalmology one of the most promising areas for the application of intelligent systems, as the diagnosis of eye diseases is largely based on the interpretation of visual data.

Modern ophthalmological examination methods, such as fundus photography, optical coherence tomography, and ultrasound biomicroscopy, generate significant image arrays, the analysis of which requires highly skilled specialists and considerable time. The use of artificial intelligence algorithms allows for the automation of the analysis process, increasing diagnostic accuracy and reducing the influence of the subjective factor associated with human perception.

Despite the obvious advantages, the implementation of artificial intelligence systems in ophthalmology is fraught with a number of challenges, including reliability, interpretability of

results, data standardization, and the integration of intelligent solutions into existing clinical protocols. Therefore, a comprehensive analysis of modern approaches to the use of artificial intelligence in ophthalmology and an assessment of its future development prospects is urgent[1].

The purpose of this article is to review and analyze the main areas of use of artificial intelligence in ophthalmology, identify its advantages and limitations, and assess the potential of intelligent technologies in improving the quality of diagnosis and treatment of visual diseases.

Fig. 1. Rosenblatt's perceptron

Fig. 2. Multiscale neural network

A dismal epilogue: Information is a concept that can have different meanings depending on the field of human activity. This is what Wikipedia says. Information in medicine is a phenomenon that is a key component determining a specialist's professional level. According to calculations by IBM, a company renowned today for its achievements in big data analysis, over 90% of the information accumulated from the advent of writing to the end of 2014 was collected in just the last two years (2012–2014), with its volume growing exponentially[2]. At the same time, simple arithmetic calculations show that mechanically reading all articles published, for example, in 15 journals with a keratorefractive profile, requires approximately 28 hours a day. This means that today information is generated in volumes that clearly do not allow a specialist to be aware of everything that is happening even in the field of practice, which forces him to be selective in his choice and which, in turn, implies an absolute probability of an error even with a phenomenal memory. At the same time, global urbanization and improving quality of life entails increasing demands on the quality of medical care, including the accuracy of diagnosis and treatment, their speed, timeliness, etc. The discrepancy between growing public expectations and

reality leads to growing discontent, an increase in the number of lawsuits, stricter legal regulation for medical workers, a deterioration in their psychological health and the quality of diagnosis and treatment[3].

“For every action, there is an equal and opposite reaction” (third law Newton). For every "negative" phenomenon, we can formulate a countervailing solution, which means it's possible to create conditions under which volumes of information impossible for the human brain can likely be compensated for. The only tool today capable of processing colossal amounts of information and producing useful results is computer technology. Throughout its existence, humanity has experienced three industrial revolutions, each of which was painful for established social norms but ultimately led to beneficial changes without which it's difficult to imagine today's prosperity. Today, we are experiencing a fourth stage, better known as “Industry 4.0”, which was first formulated in 2011 at the Hannover Fair. “Industry 4.0” is defined as the widespread implementation of computational processes in physical processes. For ophthalmology, this currently includes areas such as augmented and virtual reality in diagnostics and surgery, as well as the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in its various evolutionary modifications[4].

The most obvious and rapidly developing area of AI application today is image analysis, which originated in diagnostic radiology for oncological conditions. This was due to the urgent need to address the risk of inoperable conditions due to “low patient throughput in diagnostic rooms/delayed diagnosis/misidentification of pathological changes”. Having achieved over 80% accuracy in machine detection of pathological lesions in MRI images with IBM's Watson , this field has also seen rapid development in other areas of medicine whose diagnosis is largely based on visual manifestations, such as dermatology and ophthalmology[5].

Image recognition is essential in medicine, as the ability to automatically recognize images by computers brings many new opportunities for the advancement of science and technology, such as the development of systems for detecting and diagnosing eye diseases in photographs, quality control of applied treatments without human intervention, and automated management of functional diagnostics of ocular conditions in general. In recent years, machine learning algorithms and methods have been rapidly developing due to the significant increase in computing power of affordable computers and the widespread use of graphics cards for computing. This allows for the training of neural networks (NNs) of much greater depth and complexity than before. These networks, in turn, demonstrate significantly better results than other algorithms for many tasks, particularly image recognition. This area of NN development is known as "deep learning" and is one of the most successful and rapidly developing currently.

Now, about neural networks. In the history of neural network development, three main periods of their rise are distinguished: artificial intelligence (1950–1980), machine learning (1980–2011), and deep learning (since 2011). The first research in the field of artificial neural networks dates back to the 1940s, when in 1954 J. McCulloch and W. Pitts published the work "A Logical Calculus of Ideas Relating to Nervous Activity," which outlined the basic principles of constructing artificial neural networks. Then, in 1949, D. Hebb's book "The Organization of Behavior" was published, in which the author examined the theoretical foundations of neural network learning and first formulated the concept of their learning as the adjustment of weights between neurons. And in 1954, W. Clark made the first attempt to implement an analogue of the Hebb network using a computer. In 1958, F. Rosenblatt proposed a perceptron model, which was

essentially a neural network with one hidden layer. The basic design of Rosenblatt's perceptron is shown in Figure 1[6].

This model was trained using an error correction method, which maintained the weights as long as the perceptron output was correct. In the event of an error, the connection weight was adjusted by one in the direction opposite to the error sign. This algorithm, as Rosenblatt proved, always converges. Using this model, it was possible to create a computer that recognized some letters of the Latin alphabet, which was undoubtedly a major success at the time.

Fig. 3. Example of fundus images for analysis using neural networks

Fig. 4. Snapshot of the user interface of DeepMind software

The next stage of development of NS was the technology of “machine learning” (machine Machine learning (also known as “learning”) is based on the creation and use, with the help of an expert, of so-called “classifiers” tools that differentiate various conditions and answer the questions “normal or pathological?” and “what specific pathology?” This is “supervised learning” which assumes that, in addition to the initial data itself, the algorithm is provided with additional information about it, which it can then use for training. Classifiers operate by finding

rules for classifying objects in the form of “IF-THEN” statements. To find such rules, several main families of machine learning algorithms are typically distinguished. When it comes to classification problems, the most popular of these include, for example, rule-based classifiers, logistic regression, Bayesian classifiers, decision trees, neural networks, support vector machines, and lazy classifiers. Classification algorithms can have a wide variety of underlying ideas and naturally, demonstrate varying effectiveness for different types of problems. Thus, for tasks with a small number of input features, rule-based systems can be useful if some similarity metric can be quickly and conveniently calculated for the input objects – lazy classifiers. However, when it comes to tasks with a very large number of parameters that are also difficult to identify or interpret, such as image or speech recognition, “neural networks” become the most suitable classification method[7].

The latest evolutionary stage of neural network development today is “deep learning” (deep learning), which is trained “unsupervised”, i.e. the algorithm is not provided with any additional information from experts except the set of initial data itself. The most popular example of an “unsupervised” learning problem is the clustering problem. The essence of the clustering problem is as follows: a certain number of objects belonging to different classes are fed to the algorithm as input (but which class each object belongs to is unknown, and the number of classes may also be unknown), and the goal of the algorithm is to divide this set of objects into subsets of "similar" objects, that is, belonging to the same class. The quality of analysis using neural networks largely depends on the size of the database on which they are “trained”, i.e. the more images, the more accurate the diagnosis. Deep learning uses the convolutional neural network algorithm, which was proposed by a team consisting of Pierre Sermanet and Yann LeCun from New York University. This algorithm was in detail described V The article “Traffic Sign Recognition with Multi -Scale Convolutional Networks” describes the algorithm. In this algorithm, all source images were scaled to 32x32 pixels and converted to grayscale, after which contrast normalization was applied. The size of the initial training set was also increased by a factor of 5 by applying small random transformations to the source images. The resulting network consisted of two “stages,” as shown in Figure 2. The final classification used the output values of both the second and first stages. This network demonstrated an accuracy of 98.31%. Numerous studies have demonstrated impressively high levels of ophthalmological disease diagnostics based on the analysis of fundus photographs, optical coherence tomography data, and other data[8].

Neural Networks in Ophthalmology In ophthalmology, impressive results are already being achieved in the analysis of such pathological eye conditions as diabetic retinopathy (DRP), age-related macular degeneration, macular edema, glaucoma, cataracts, and others. Color fundus images, fluorescein angiography (FA) and autofluorescence images, optical coherence tomography (OCT) scans, and visual fields are analyzed.

DRP was the “pilot” pathology for testing the capabilities of neural networks, since as it develops, it acquires a number of clearly visualized changes that are convenient for “training” the neural network. Thus, in the work “Development” and Validation of a Deep Learning Algorithm for Detection of Diabetic Retinopathy in Retinal Fundus Photographs, the software (software) trained on 128,000 fundus images (Fig. 3) demonstrated an F-measure level of 0.95 (a combined parameter of sensitivity and specificity, where the maximum is 1.0), the practical significance of which is difficult to ignore.

Fig. 4 shows the result of the software developed by the DeepMind division of Google , which is one of the pioneers in the field of deep learning in the field of ophthalmology. The analysis of 15 thousand OCT scans allowed the developers to write software that performs a parallel analysis of several retinal diseases at once and provides the doctor with information on the probability of the presence of one or another, based on the ratio of pathological signs that may be characteristic of several diseases. This example shows the detection of changes that are 99.5% (according to the internal criteria of the program) consistent with chryoid Neovascularization , as well as the degree of urgency of the disease, which can be used in screening examinations. This work also demonstrated the feasibility and significance of parallel analysis of multiple parametric factors, which significantly reduces the likelihood of error by eliminating accidentally detected individual variables that may be characteristic of a particular disease.

Prospects. Today's computing capabilities make it possible to implement calculations on a scale never before possible. For example, compiling multiple diagnostic data for a disease such as glaucoma in calculations can allow not only the detection of the disease itself but also the prediction of the possible outcome, the aggressiveness of the disease, the effect of a specific type of treatment, etc., as well as identify previously unknown criteria inherent in the disease that may be critical in patient management, which is achievable using deep learning algorithms. Such solutions can be applied in virtually all areas of ophthalmology, thereby elevating healthcare capabilities to a fundamentally new level.

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